

Dripsody — Hugh Le Caine

Jason Noble, 2018

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<https://timbreandorchestration.org/writings/amazing-moments-in-timbre/2018/11/30/dripsody>

Our second Amazing Moment in Timbre is another classic, but somewhat lesser-known. It's Canadian composer and inventor Hugh Le Caine's *Dripsody* (1955). A great early example of *musique concrète*—music made from recordings of real-world sounds that may be manipulated in various ways—Le Caine built up astonishing musical textures from a single recording of a drop of water. He had to physically cut, paste, splice, and loop magnetic tape to achieve the musical result, which may seem like a tremendous feat of labour intensity to those of us now accustomed to digital audio workstations on personal computers. Enjoy!

Video: <https://youtu.be/zvHSvSBwFYM>